

Green new-developmentalism: recent contributions and a research agenda

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Abstract

The aim of this article is to present the recent theoretical contributions for the So-Called Green new Developmentalism created by Guarini and Oreiro (2023) and analyse how this theoretical framework can be to address the transition problem for a low-carbon economy. The New Developmentalism (ND), which emerged from the original contributions of Bresser-Pereira, Oreiro and Marconi (2015), establishes that middle-income countries such as Brazil have gone through a process of early deindustrialization in the last 30 years due to the exchange rate overvaluation derived from the Dutch disease (DD), that is, the abundance of natural resources (such as, for example, iron ore and soybeans) in a context of almost unrestricted opening of the capital account of the balance of payments. ND, however, has never explored a little-known face of DD, namely that this problem is associated with environmental degradation, contributing to the problem of global warming. In other words, ND did not concern itself with the issue of the environmental sustainability of the development process. The ecological sustainability of economic development concerns the long-term improvement of living standards, considering a polyhedron of social, economic and environmental elements. A structural view of ecological sustainability should focus not on the static problem of resource scarcity and resource allocation through market mechanisms, but on the dynamic problem of resource creation, driven by aggregate demand and its limits.

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1. Introduction

Green New Developmentalism (GND) emerges as a theoretical evolution and a strategic response to the limitations of the original new developmentalist framework, developed in the last 15 years from the seminal work of Bresser-Pereira (2006, 2007, 2009), for the problem of climate change caused by emissions of Green House Gases (GHG) in the atmosphere. The formal starting point for this branch of New-Developmentalism (ND) can be traced to the publication of the article "An ecological view of New Developmentalism: a proposal of integration" by Giulio Guarini and José Luis Oreiro in the *Brazilian Journal of Political Economy* in 2022. This seminal contribution represented a deliberate move to incorporate the environmental aspects of economic development into both the core of theoretical new-developmental growth models² as well as on the development strategy for developing countries that had fallen into the middle-income trap (Guarini and Oreiro, 2023).

New Developmentalism (ND) offered a powerful diagnosis for the economic stagnation of middle-income countries, such as Brazil, linking it to exchange rate overvaluation and premature deindustrialisation (Bresser-Pereira, Oreiro and Marconi, 2015). However, by focusing almost exclusively on the macroeconomic aspects of economic development, ND had nothing to say about environmental sustainability. In this sense, ND shared with traditional neoclassical economics as well as classical political economy the vision of the economy to be a **closed system** with no interaction with natural environment. The promotion of reindustrialisation, one of the most important policy recommendations of ND for countries that had fallen in the Middle-Income-Trap (MIT) could simply accelerate ecological degradation if it is based in brown industries, that is, industries that had a lower environmental efficiency, defined as GHG emissions per unit of output produced (Guarini and Oreiro, 2023). The work of Guarini and Oreiro (2022, 2023) solved this problem by reformulating the “protecting belt” of the ND **Research Program** (Lakatos, 1978) without changing its hard core, contributing to characterize ND as a progressive Research Program.

Indeed, this evolution can be understood as a *progressive problem shift* in the terms of Lakatos (1978). The new developmentalist research programme, led by Bresser-Pereira and Oreiro amongst others, demonstrated its vitality by applying its central framework to solve a new "puzzle" or "anomaly"—the climate crisis—which the original model could not satisfactorily explain or solve. In doing so, GND does not abandon the fundamental principles of ND but expands and qualifies them, proposing a development strategy that seeks to reconcile economic growth, social inclusion, and respect for the planet's biophysical limits, with the aim of identifying a *balanced ecological growth path* (Grazini, Guarini and Oreiro, 2024)

² The most complete growth model of the New-Developmentalist literature can be seen in Oreiro, Martins da Silva and Dávila-Fernandez (2020).

The intellectual lineage of GND is a *heterodox triumvirate*³, merging three distinct traditions of heterodox economic thought:

- I) **Post-Keynesianism:** From this tradition, GND inherits the principle of effective demand as the long-term driver of economic growth, the importance of macroeconomic policy for demand management, and the analysis of investment in a context of fundamental uncertainty. Oreiro's deep grounding in the Cambridge Post-Keynesian tradition and Guarini's experience in Post-Keynesian modelling are determining influences, connecting the developmentalist debate to a broader theoretical body
- II) **Latin American Structuralism:** GND adopts the focus of ECLAC structuralism on structural change as the engine of development, the analysis of centre-periphery dynamics, and the identification of barriers to industrialisation, such as Dutch Disease (Guarini and Oreiro, 2023). Development is understood as a process of structural change or reallocating resources from lower-productivity activities with lower level of sophistication to higher-productivity and technologically sophisticated ones (Bresser-Pereira, Oreiro and Marconi, 2015).
- III) **Ecological Economics:** This strand introduces into the model an awareness of biophysical limits, the imperative need to decouple economic growth from environmental degradation, and the operational concepts of environmental pressure and efficiency. This integration allows the model to go beyond purely economic constraints and incorporate planetary limits as a determining factor in the development trajectory.

The synthesis of these three currents allows GND to offer a broader analysis and a more robust policy strategy, positioning itself as a coherent alternative to both economic orthodoxy and developmentalist approaches that ignore the ecological dimension.

2. Ecological Structural Change (ESC) and Ecological Technological Progress (ETP)

One of the most important analytical innovations of Green New Developmentalism is the clear distinction between two complementary but distinct processes that form the basis of the transition to a sustainable economy: Ecological Structural Change (ESC) and Ecological Technological Progress (ETP)⁴. This distinction allowed to move beyond a simplistic view focused only on "green technology" and to understand the green transition as a profound process of transforming the productive structure of the economy.

³ See

<https://jilcoreiro.wordpress.com/2025/06/30/green-new-developmentalism-an-analysis-of-its-theoretical-evolution-and-policy-implications/>

⁴ Guarini and Oreiro (2022).

Ecological Structural Change (ESC) is defined as the reallocation of economic resources (capital and labour) from activities with high environmental pressure intensity ('the so-called brown' sectors) to activities with low environmental pressure intensity (the so-called 'green' sectors). This is the core of the GND strategy (Grazini and Guarini, 2025). It is not just about making existing economic activities cleaner, but about changing the composition of GDP, increasing the share of industries and services that are more efficient from an environmental standpoint. This process is not only technological; it encompasses a social dimension, associated with the evolution of consumer and institutional preferences for green products and processes, and an institutional dimension, which shapes the rules of the game to favour sustainable production (Dávila-Dávila and Dávila-Fernandez, 2024)

Ecological Technological Progress (ETP), in turn, is defined as the increase in environmental efficiency *within* any sector, defined as the ratio of the flow of pollution, GHG emissions and environmental degradation (per year) and output (Guarini and Oreiro, 2023), whether the sector be 'brown' or 'green'. It results from innovations that allow for the reduction of GHG emissions, energy consumption, or the use of natural resources per unit of output. For example, a steel mill (a brown sector) that adopts a new technology to reduce its GHG emissions is contributing to ETP. Similarly, a solar panel factory (a green sector) that develops a production process that uses less energy is also promoting ETP.

The synergy and interaction between ESC and ETP are crucial and have been formalised in models. In the work of Guarini and Oreiro (2023), published in *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences*, the total environmental pressure of the economy (EPED) is modelled as a weighted average of the pressure from the green (EP1) and brown (EP2) sectors, where the weights are their respective shares in GDP. The fundamental equation is given by:

$$EPED = [EP_1\epsilon + EP_2(1 - \epsilon)]Y \quad (1)$$

Where: Y is real output or GDP, ϵ is the share of green sectors in GDP.

In equation (1) we can see the dynamics of ecological sustainability. The total environmental pressure can decrease through three channels:

1. A reduction in EP1 and EP2, which represents *Ecological Technological Progress* (ETP).
2. An increase in ϵ (the share of the green sector), which represents *Ecological Structural Change* (ESC).
3. A reduction in Y (GDP), which would be the *degrowth approach*.

GND focuses on the first two channels. The equation (1) also demonstrates that ETP alone could be insufficient. Even if technology becomes cleaner (reduction of EP1

and EP2), robust GDP growth (Y) or stagnation in structural change (ϵ constant) can lead to an increase in total environmental pressure. Therefore, the simultaneous and deliberate promotion of ESC and ETP is the only way to reconcile economic growth with environmental sustainability within the GND paradigm. This formalisation transforms environmental policy from a sectoral issue to a central macroeconomic one, demonstrating the need for a productive transformation strategy to achieve ecological goals.

3. Environmental Degradation the forgotten side of Dutch Disease.

Green New Developmentalism establishes a causal connection between Dutch Disease (DD) and environmental degradation, arguing that they are two sides of the same macro-structural problem of middle-income economies rich in natural resources (Guarini and Oreiro, 2022b). The traditional theory of DD focuses on how the abundance of natural resources leads to a chronic overvaluation of the real exchange rate, which in turn undermines the price competitiveness of the manufacturing sector, leading to premature deindustrialisation.

GND expands this analysis by demonstrating that exchange rate overvaluation not only harms manufacturing industry but also creates negative economic incentives that accelerate environmental degradation. The specialisation in primary commodities—such as soy, beef, and iron ore, whose export causes the exchange rate to appreciate—drives the expansion of the agricultural and mining frontiers over natural ecosystems (Grazini, Guarini and Oreiro, 2024). For the specific case of Brazil, this dynamics is the main cause of deforestation and, consequently, of most of its greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, which come from land-use change.¹⁵ Exchange rate overvaluation makes the conversion of forests into pastures and croplands a more profitable activity than investing in manufacturing (Guarini and Oreiro, 2022).

Furthermore, an overvalued exchange rate acts as a direct barrier to Ecological Structural Change (ESC). Infant 'green industries', which are often more technology-intensive, with higher capital costs and longer maturation horizons, are particularly vulnerable to international competition. An overvalued exchange rate can make their goods not competitive in both domestic and foreign markets, stifling the ecological transition before it can even begin.

Therefore, DD and environmental degradation are not separate problems to be solved by distinct policies (one for exchange rates and another for the environment). They are seen as dual and interconnected consequences of the same macroeconomic failure. The same force that causes premature 'brown' deindustrialisation also prevents 'green' reindustrialisation and encourages environmental destruction. This integrated understanding is fundamental to the policy formulation of GND, which seeks to attack the root cause—the unbalance of the economy's key relative prices, especially the exchange rate—rather than just mitigating its symptoms.

4. The Ecological Sustainable Rate of Growth and Macroeconomic Growth Models

One of the most significant theoretical contributions of GND is the formalisation and integration of an ecological constraint directly into heterodox macroeconomic growth models. This is done through the introduction of the concept of the *ecologically sustainable growth rate* (Grazini, Guarini and Oreiro, 2024). This growth rate is defined as the maximum rate of real output growth that is compatible with a stable concentration of GHGs in the atmosphere at a level that prevents catastrophic climate change (e.g., aligned with the 1.5°C target of the Paris Agreement). Operationally, this implies a *net-zero emissions growth path*, where the gross emissions generated by economic activity are offset by carbon absorption capacity⁵

This concept is then incorporated into a Post-Keynesian-Structuralist Macroeconomic Framework that considers traditional growth constraints, mainly the capacity constraint and the balance of payments constraint (Blecker and Setterfield, 2019).

The capacity constraint is given by the *warranted rate of growth* (g_w), derived from the Harrod-Domar model (Oreiro, 2018). The *warranted rate of growth* is the growth rate of real output for which the growth rate of effective demand is equal to the growth rate of productive capacity, holding the capacity utilization constant at a normal or long-run level (Oreiro, 2018, chapter 3). The *warranted rate of growth* is given by the ratio between investment rate and capital-output coefficient minus the depreciation rate of capital stock.

The balance of payments constraint is the growth rate of real output for which the current account as a ratio of GDP is kept constant at a level that is sustainable in the long-run (Thirlwall, 2002, 2013). The *balance-of-payments-constrained growth rate* (G_{BPCG}) is given by the so-called *Thirlwall's Law* according to which the *balance-of-payments-constrained growth rate* is given by the ratio of income elasticities of exports and imports multiplied by the growth rate of worlds' income (Thirlwall, 2002, 2013).

A balanced growth path requires the equalization of *warranted rate of growth* with *balance-of-payments-constrained growth rate* in order to achieve a stable capacity utilization at a normal long-run level as well as the intertemporal equilibrium of balance of payments. This balanced growth path will be *ecologically sustainable* if the growth rate of real output is compatible with a zero-net emissions of GHG in order to maintain the increase in global temperature at a tolerable level in the long-run. Furthermore, the balanced growth path must also be socially inclusive in order to allow a steady reduction in global poverty and income inequality as well as to create job opportunities for an increasing global population.

⁵ See [Green New Developmentalism: An Analysis of its Theoretical Evolution and Policy Implications | José Luis Oreiro](#)

This analysis of GND culminates in the formulation of a **development trilemma**, which represents the central challenge for development policy in the 21st century. Development policy must be able to manage and reconcile three distinct growth rates, which can be conflicting, that is:

1. The *balance-of-payments-constrained growth rate* (G_{BPCG}) which represents the external constraint.
2. The *minimum growth rate necessary for social inclusion* (g_s), which represents the social constraint (job creation, poverty and inequality reduction).
3. The *maximum ecologically sustainable growth rate* (g_E), which represents the biophysical constraint.

The consideration of the ecological constraint (g_E) as a policy target on an equal basis with the external and social constraints, is a paradigmatic shift. It transforms the problem of sustainability from an externality to be corrected into a fundamental condition for the sustainability and stability of long-term growth. The objective of GND's macroeconomic and development policy then becomes to find a *balanced ecological growth path* where the actual growth rate of the real output is consistent with all three constraints. Overcoming the potential trade-offs between these goals -for example, a situation in which the growth rate compatible with social inclusion is higher than the *maximum ecologically sustainable growth rate* - is only possible through ESC and ETP, which alter the parameters of the model itself (such as the carbon intensity of GDP and the composition of GDP between green and brown sectors), allowing for faster and, at the same time, cleaner growth. The development trilemma, therefore, is not just a descriptive tool but a powerful justification for the need for a green industrial, technological policy and macroeconomic policy.

5. The Coordination of Macroeconomic Policy for Ecological and Social Sustainability.

Green New Developmentalism proposes a break with the conventional approach of rules-based macroeconomic policy, advocating for an activist, integrated, and synergistic policy mix designed specifically to promote Ecological Structural Change (Grazini et al, 2025). The central premise is that environmental sustainability cannot be achieved through sectoral environmental policies alone if the structure of macroeconomic incentives pulls in the opposite direction. Therefore, exchange rate, fiscal, and monetary policies must be coordinated and aligned with the strategic objective of green reindustrialisation.

5.1 The Centrality of Exchange Rate Policy

The cornerstone of the GND strategy is the active management of the real exchange rate to keep it at a competitive and stable level. An overvalued exchange rate,

a consequence of Dutch Disease, is identified as the main obstacle to productive diversification and the ecological transition. It undermines the price-competitiveness of any infant green industries, which already face higher costs and greater uncertainty, making them unable to compete with imports or access foreign markets. Instead of being used as an anchor to control inflation, exchange rate policy must be a central instrument of the development strategy. To neutralise DD, GND proposes instruments such as export taxes on primary commodities. Such taxes would have the dual benefit of alleviating the overvaluation on the exchange rate and, at the same time, reducing the profitability of environmentally predatory activities, such as the expansion of the agricultural frontier in the direction of rain forests (Grazini, Guarini and Oreiro, 2024).

5.2 Activist Fiscal Policy: Investment and Incentives

Fiscal policy in the GND framework plays a dual and proactive role: financing the ecological transition and creating the right incentives for the private sector. This manifests in three main areas:

- **Green Public Investment:** The state must lead a vast programme of public and private investment in the decarbonisation of the economy. Public investment is considered essential to finance sustainable infrastructure (renewable energy, public transport), research and development (R&D) in clean technologies, and natural capital projects (reforestation, bioeconomy). These investments are crucial because the private sector, on its own, would not undertake them at the necessary scale or speed, due to high risk, long maturation horizons, and fundamental uncertainty.
- **Carbon Pricing and Tax Reform:** GND advocates for the use of carbon pricing instruments, such as emissions taxes or emissions trading systems, to internalise the negative environmental externalities of pollution. This should be accompanied by the removal of subsidies for the production and consumption of fossil fuels, which distort prices and delay the transition.
- **Fiscal Flexibility for Green Investment:** A *green investment push* must be compatible with fiscal responsibility. However, GND argues that fiscal rules should be designed flexibly to accommodate the strategic investments needed for the climate transition. These expenditures should not be treated as current expenditures but as capital investments in the country's future productive capacity and resilience and therefore excluded from spending caps or primary surplus targets.

5.3. Accommodative Monetary and Financial Policy

Monetary policy and the financial system must be designed to achieve sustainable development objectives. The orthodox view of an independent central bank focused exclusively on inflation control is inadequate for promoting the required structural transformation. In GND, monetary and financial policy acts through:

- **Development Banks:** Institutions like the National Bank for Economic and Social

Development (BNDES) in Brazil are seen as crucial actors. They must provide patient, long-term capital for green investments, act counter-cyclically to stabilise investment in periods of recessions, and, fundamentally, 'de-risk' innovative projects that the private financial system considers too risky to finance.

- **Directed Credit and Differentiated Interest Rates:** GND suggests the use of directed credit lines, with potentially subsidised interest rates, to channel resources to priority green sectors. This challenges the view of a single monetary policy that affects all sectors in the same way, recognising that the transition requires preferential treatment for strategic activities. Financial regulation is also seen as an important instrument to accelerate and increase the volume of green investments.

5.4. The Imperative of Policy Integration

The strongest and most radical message of GND is that none of these policies can be effective if are taken in an uncoordinated and isolated way. Robust and strategic coordination between fiscal, monetary, exchange rate, industrial, and environmental policies is a *sine qua non* for success. An exchange rate devaluation without an industrial policy that increases supply capacity can lead to inflation. Public investment in green sectors without a competitive exchange rate may be ineffective, as new companies will not be able to survive. Industrial policy without long-term financing from development banks is impossible to implement.

This vision represents a fundamental break with the neoliberal paradigm of independent and isolated institutions. The logic of GND demonstrates that the separation of mandates could be counterproductive. If the central bank raises interest rates to control inflation, it can make unprofitable the green investment that fiscal and industrial policy is trying to promote. If exchange rate overvalues due to a commodity boom, it undermines the price-competitiveness of the infant green industries that are being subsidised. Coordination, therefore, is not an option but a logical necessity of the model. This implies a profound reassessment of institutional mandates and the rejection of the idea that macroeconomic policy is neutral for long-term growth. Macroeconomic policy must be not only developmentalist but also green, requiring a new governance capacity and robust institutional arrangements to prevent interest group capture and ensure synergy.

6. The Role of Land-Use Change in the GND Strategy

The Green New Developmentalism strategy addresses the issue of land-use change (LUC)—the main source of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in countries like Brazil—not as an isolated problem of environmental enforcement, but as a direct consequence of fundamental macroeconomic imbalances (Guarini and Oreiro, 2022; Martins da Silva, Oreiro e Teixeira, 2024). Deforestation for the expansion of agriculture and livestock is seen as the logical result of a set of perverse economic incentives, fuelled by Dutch Disease.

As analysed in Section 3, the overvaluation of the exchange rate, driven by commodity exports, makes the expansion of the agricultural frontier over natural ecosystems a much more profitable activity than investment in manufacturing. In this scenario, command-and-control policies (such as fines and enforcement), although necessary, are insufficient to contain the economic pressure on forests. If it is immensely profitable to deforest, economic agents will find ways to circumvent regulation.

The solution proposed by GND, therefore, attacks the root cause of the problem: distorted relative prices. The strategy seeks to transform land-use change from an emissions vector into a mitigation tool by fundamentally altering the structure of macroeconomic incentives. The main instrument for this is the *neutralisation of Dutch Disease*. One of the central proposals is the implementation of an **export tax on primary products**, such as soybeans, iron-ore and beef. This tax would have a dual strategic objective:

1. **Macroeconomic objective:** By taxing commodity exports, the tax helps to alleviate the overvaluation pressure on the exchange rate, contributing to maintaining a more competitive level that favours green manufacturing industry.
2. **Environmental objective:** By reducing the net revenue from the export of agricultural products, the tax directly decreases the profitability of expanding the agricultural frontier, discouraging deforestation.

At the same time, the other policies in the GND mix—such as a competitive exchange rate, directed credit, and public investment in R&D—work to create and strengthen a viable economic alternative: the green industry and the bioeconomy. In this new scenario of relative prices, where extensive agriculture becomes less profitable and sustainable industrial production becomes more attractive, the *opportunity cost* of keeping the forest standing decreases dramatically.

Moreover, the conversion of degraded pastures and low-productivity agricultural areas into forests—**reforestation**—ceases to be just an environmental cost and can become a profitable economic activity. In a world that carbon emissions have a price, standing and recovering forests generate value through carbon credits, in addition to opening up opportunities for the sustainable exploitation of biodiversity products (bioeconomy).

Thus, the GND's approach to land-use change is profoundly structural. It does not isolate the environmental problem from the economic context. On the contrary, it understands that the forest will only be protected in a lasting way when the country's economic structure does not depend on its destruction. Land-use change, from a source of emissions to a carbon sink, becomes an endogenous outcome of the macroeconomic strategy of green reindustrialisation, and not just the objective of a sectoral and reactive environmental policy.

Final Remarks

Green New Developmentalism (GND) establishes itself as a coherent and progressive heterodox research programme, offering a robust response to the interconnected challenges of economic development and environmental sustainability in middle-income countries. By innovatively integrating the legacies of post-Keynesianism, structuralism, and ecological economics, GND reframes the developmentalist debate. It transcends the traditional ND view focused on the exchange rate constraint to propose a strategy of structural transformation aimed at green reindustrialisation, driven by an activist and coordinated macroeconomic policy. Its central tenets—Ecological Structural Change and Ecological Technological Progress—and its formalisation of an 'ecologically sustainable growth rate' represent significant theoretical contributions that incorporates biophysical limits as a central variable for macroeconomic and development debates.

The policy implications of GND are profound and require a paradigmatic break with the economic orthodoxy that has dominated recent decades. The implementation of its agenda presupposes a State with high technical and governance capacity, capable of formulating and executing a national *green development strategy* (Oreiro, Teixeira and Ferreira-Filho, 2023). This requires a significant institutional reconfiguration to overcome policy fragmentation and enable synergistic coordination between the exchange rate, fiscal, monetary, and industrial areas. The rejection of macroeconomic policy neutrality and the advocacy for institutional mandates aligned with sustainable development place GND in direct confrontation with the neoliberal consensus, making its implementation a political challenge of great magnitude.

Despite its comprehensiveness, the GND framework presents important avenues for future research. Firstly, the political economy dimension of the transition deserves more detailed modelling. The analysis of distributional conflicts between 'green' and 'brown' sectors, skilled and unskilled workers, and different regional interests is crucial for understanding the political feasibility of the strategy (Grazini, Guarini and Porcile, 2024). Secondly, the impacts of the green transition on the labour market, income inequality, and poverty require more in-depth empirical and theoretical investigation. Finally, for the GND strategy to be globally viable, a more explicit engagement with the debate on international coordination is necessary. The development of these research areas will further strengthen GND as an intellectual and political alternative for a more prosperous, just, and sustainable future.

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